

CHRONIC BRONCHITIS

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Annotation: This scientific article is about the etiology, pathogenesis, clinical forms of chronic obstructive bronchitis, clinical signs observed in patients with chronic obstructive bronchitis, laboratory instrumental and physical examination methods, methods of treatment of patients with chronic obstructive bronchitis, and consists of a clinical analysis of this disease.

Keywords: Chronic bronchitis, chronic polyposis, sputum, chronic deforming, nonallergic, X-ray, spirometry, bronchoscopy
Introduction: Chronic bronchitis (SB) is a diffuse progressive nonallergic inflammatory disease of the bronchial wall accompanied by cough. Patients with sputum cough for at least 3 months per year for 2 years are included in the category of SB patients. Prevalence: 80% of all diseases of the respiratory system, 50% of disability due to diseases of the respiratory system. Etiology: tobacco smoke, air pollution, climatic factors, infection, nasopharyngeal pathology, nasal breathing disorder, frequent acute respiratory disease and acute bronchitis, genetic predisposition, obesity (local immunity and metabolic disorders at the expense of). In the pathogenesis of chronic bronchitis, the violation of the secretory, cleaning and protective functions of the bronchial mucosa plays a key role, which leads to changes in mucociliary transport.

Characteristic symptoms of chronic bronchitis are cough with sputum (phlegm or mucus), shortness of breath. Cough is worse in the morning (more severe cough when smoking). Sputum is secreted in large quantities in the morning ("full mouth") and in the amount of up to 100 ml per day. Check: there may be no obvious symptoms; Palpation: sound vibration does not change or is evenly reduced; Percussion: In SB, the percussion sound does not change; Auscultation can be both intensified and weakened, characterized by harsh breathing, scattered dry and wet wheezes (can change localization or disappear after coughing) wheezing. When the heart tones are weakened or the disease worsens, the tones are not heard at all.

Arrhythmia can be detected. The main morphological types of SB:

1. Chronic mucous (mucous purulent)
2. Chronic polyposis

3. Chronic deforming
Chronic obstructive bronchitis (SOB) is the main and most characteristic manifestation of cough. It usually lasts at least three months a

year, worsens at night, but is not accompanied by sore throat or redness. The disease is also associated with other unpleasant symptoms. Thus, most of the patients complain: Shortness of breath and lack of air during breathing; Itching of the throat, Weakness, Sputum discharge when coughing, Acute symptoms of the disease are observed in acute periods: Increased body temperature, Shivering. SOB is a chronic progressive disease, which is based on degenerative-inflammatory non-allergic damage to the mucous membrane of the tracheobronchial tree, which usually develops as a result of long-term irritation of the airways by harmful substances with the restructuring of secretions, and this sclerotic changes in the bronchial apparatus and bronchial wall. It is characterized by cough with sputum production for at least 3 months for more than 2 consecutive years; the diagnosis is made after excluding other possible causes of persistent cough.

The most important risk factors for SOB are smoking, tobacco smoke, and ozone. This is followed by dust and chemicals in the workplace (irritants, vapors), residential air pollution with fossil fuel combustion products, ambient air pollution, passive smoking, respiratory tract infections in early childhood, shortness of breath increases gradually during exercise. The main clinical manifestations of SOB are: Cough with muco-purulent sputum up to 100-150 ml, mainly in the morning; In the stage of strengthening - general weakness, rapid fatigue; With purulent bronchitis - an increase in body temperature;

Exacerbation of SB is a stable increase in the intensity of symptoms compared to the usual steady state, in which the variability of symptoms exceeds the daily and develops acutely. Currently, the relevance of the results of the research conducted by N. Antonisen and scientists remains relevant, according to which there are three types of increased SB: Type I - characterized by increased shortness of breath, increased sputum volume and increased purulence; Type II - the presence of two of these symptoms, i.e. increased shortness of breath and increased sputum Type III - one of these symptoms in addition to one of the following symptoms: upper respiratory tract infection in the last 5 days, unexplained fever, wheezing, or increased cough, increased heart rate or respiratory rate by 20% compared to the initial state, this is one of the most common respiratory diseases. In addition to coughing, the patient complains of fatigue, sweating, aggravation at night, general weakness. After some time (it has a different value for everyone), symptoms of bronchial obstruction develop: dry or ineffective cough; shortness of breath, in which breathing is prolonged; an increase in the rate of breathing more than the age norm. Cough in the clinic (in

the morning with increased secretion of a small amount of sputum, purulent and purulent sputum, restlessness, sweating, tachycardia, low-grade fever, shortness of breath) - on auscultation of the lungs - vesicular breath. ; during exacerbation - dry "whispering" and inaudible wheezing Laboratory-instrumental diagnosis of chronic bronchitis General blood analysis: exacerbation of purulent bronchitis, moderate increase in ECHT, leukocytosis with a shift to the left. Biochemical analysis of blood: exacerbation of purulent bronchitis, increased blood levels of fibrin, seromucoid, alpha and gamma globulins (in rare cases). General sputum analysis: light-colored mucous sputum, yellowish-green purulent sputum, mucous-purulent plugs, with OB - bronchial epitheliocytes can be detected; microscopic examination of purulent sputum - many neutrophils. In SOB, the alkaline reaction of the morning sputum and the neutral or acidic reaction of the daytime sputum are noted. At the initial stage of the disease, sputum is usually mucous. With the development of SB, the sputum becomes purulent or purulent, which is especially noticeable during the exacerbation of the disease. Rheological properties of sputum: purulent sputum - increase in viscosity, decrease in elasticity; mucous sputum - decrease in viscosity, increase in elasticity. Kurschmann spirals can be identified with OB.

Spirography: changes in the spirogram depend on the severity of the disturbance of the external respiratory function, the vital capacity of the lungs usually decreases. Primary SB should be compared with secondary bronchitis with long-term cough and wheezing in other diseases (lung cancer, bronchiectasis, BA, pulmonary tuberculosis, chronic pneumonia). 1. Unlike chronic asthma, SB is a diffuse disease that gradually causes bronchial obstruction, O'E, shortness of breath, and pulmonary hypertension. X-ray changes in this disease are mainly diffuse changes in the bronchial tree and are represented by bronchial obstruction and obstructive emphysema. 2. It differs from BA in the absence of suffocation attacks. 3. In chronic asthma, the inflammatory process is determined only in a limited part of lung tissue, and cases of pneumosclerosis and carnification are observed. 4. In comparison with pulmonary tuberculosis: it is based on the symptoms of tuberculosis intoxication (poisoning) in the patient, the presence of mycobacterium tuberculosis (cocci) in the sputum, the data of X-ray and bronchoscopy examinations and the results of tuberculin tests. Among the aminopenicillins most often prescribed for the treatment of SB, amoxicillin produced by OJSC "Sintez" under the trademark Amosin®, OJSC "Sintez", Kurgan has optimal bioavailability, so it has an advantage over ampicillin, which has a much lower bioavailability. Protected

penicillins (amoxicillin / clavulanic acid 0.625 g orally every 8 hours, ampicillin / sulbactam 3 gx 4 times a day IV); Cephalosporins 1-2 generations (cefazolin IV 2 x 3 times a day, cefuroxime 0.75 x 3 times IV); Pathogenetic treatment is aimed at: 1) improving lung ventilation; 2) restoration of bronchial permeability; 3) Fight against LV and right ventricular failure

Conclusion: This scientific article has scientifically studied and analyzed the etiology, pathogenesis, clinical forms of chronic obstructive bronchitis, clinical signs observed in patients with chronic obstructive bronchitis, laboratory instrumental and physical examination methods, treatment methods for patients with chronic obstructive bronchitis .

References:

1. O'.Sharapov, F.G'afforova "Ichki kasalliklar" 2006 p6-14
2. S.Babajanov "Ichki kasalliklar" p15-24
3. Meduniver.com

